

Treatment	Quantity/ha per round	Navarai 1984-85			Sornavari 1985			
		GLH (no./hill)	Grasshopper (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	GLH mortality (%)	GM silver shoots (%)	SB whiteheads (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Neem seed kernel extract, 2%	10 kg	1.9 (1.39) a	9.4 (17.83) b	5.8 a	58.9 (50.07) b	7.2 (15.57) a	25.0 (29.98) bc	6.6
Neem cake extract, 5%	25 kg	2.7 (1.65) b	8.9 (17.33) ab	4.9 b	45.2 (42.24) c	8.3 (16.74) b	25.9 (31.60) cd	6.0
Neem leaf extract, 5%	25 kg	2.4 (1.54) ab	5.9 (14.05) a	5.1 b	66.6 (54.71) a	8.8 (17.25) b	22.3 (28.15) b	6.2
Phosphamidon 100 EC	500 ml	2.9 (1.70) b	9.8 (18.22) b	5.4 ab	63.6 (52.90) a	13.0 (21.13) c	12.5 (20.65) a	6.3
Control	-	4.7 (2.17) c	15.5 (23.21) c	5.1 b	10.9 (19.28) d	29.2 (32.71) d	30.4 (33.46) d	5.7
CD		(0.30)	(3.68)	0.59	(2.33)	(1.05)	(2.80)	ns

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed values.

randomized block design. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TM8089 and TKM 9 were planted in 3- × 3-m plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. These were fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. Three spray applications were made 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting. Infestations by green leafhopper (GLH), stem borer (SB), gall

midge (GM), and grasshoppers were assessed at periodic intervals. Data on pest incidence and grain yield were analyzed statistically.

Results indicated that the neem products effectively controlled the major rice pests and were even superior to phosphamidon in controlling GM,

GLH, and grasshoppers (see table). However, phosphamidon was superior to neem products in controlling SB. Plots sprayed with 2% neem seed kernel extract had the highest grain yields of 5.8 and 6.6 t/ha in navarai and sornavari seasons, respectively. *ℓ*

Effect of neem oil on germination and sporulation of the entomogenous fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae*

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Entomogenous fungi are important biological control agents that can infect insect pests and reduce their populations. We are evaluating them for possible control of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and black bug *Scotinophara coarctata*. However, the effectiveness of naturally occurring and artificially applied fungi may be seriously affected by chemical applications.

We sought to determine the effect of neem oil on the germination and sporulation of *Metarhizium anisopliae*, an entomopathogenic fungus that infects several important rice insect pests.

Conidia germination was observed in a liquid medium (1% saccharose/1% yeast extract) with 0, 5, 50, and 95%

Inhibitory effect of neem oil on germination and sporulation of *M. anisopliae*.

neem oil. Each treatment had five replications. Small amounts of conidia were added to the medium, which then was incubated for 24 h in vials on a rotary shaker. Germination was evaluated under a microscope.

Mycelium sporulation was studied by soaking dry mycelium particles in

concentrations of neem oil similar to those of the germination experiment. The particles were incubated on moist filter paper in petri dishes. Evaluation was concurrent with completion of sporulation in the control treatment (no neem oil).

Virtually all the mycelium particles

contained the characteristic layer of green conidia. The highest neem oil concentration completely inhibited both conidia germination and mycelium sporulation (see figure). The effects of neem oil at lower concentration were not so severe but even at 5% concentration, neem significantly

($P < 0.01$) inhibited germination and sporulation.

Neem oil normally is applied in the field as an ultralow volume spray containing up to 50% of the oil. If it is used in a control program with *M. anisopliae*, they should be applied separately.

Although the inhibitory effects of neem oil on entomogenous fungi have not been tested in the field, it is likely that neem at high concentrations may reduce the overall effectiveness of naturally occurring entomopathogenic fungi. \mathcal{J}

Relative abundance of three species of egg parasitoids of rice brown planthopper (BPH)

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Egg parasitoids of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. such as *Anagrus optabilis* (Perkins) (Mymaridae), *Oligosita niais* Girault (Trichogrammatidae), and egg predator *Tetrastichus* spp. (Eulophidae) are common in Tamil Nadu between Sep and Jan when climatic conditions are optimum for the host.

Potted rice plants laden with BPH eggs were placed in the field periodically between Oct and Dec 1984. Eggs were collected (see table) from the sheaths and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish for further development. The BPH emerging from normal eggs were recorded daily and removed immediately. Similarly, the larvae of *Tetrastichus* spp. were periodically

Relative occurrence of the three egg parasitoidal predators of BPH, Oct-Dec 1984.

Period	Total eggs observed (no.)	Parasitization (%)	Parasitization (%) by species		
			<i>Anagrus</i> sp.	<i>Tetrastichus</i> sp.	<i>Oligosita</i> sp.
1 Oct	567	49	60	35	3
18 Oct	602	40	58	29	13
27 Oct	551	74	72	4	23
3 Nov	416	46	57	15	27
24 Nov	717	4	57	34	8
4 Dec	463	44	62	23	14
19 Dec	376	35	48	24	27
28 Dec	544	42	51	19	
	\bar{X}	47	58	23	18
			27	11	8

removed and recorded as soon as the 1st-instar larvae emerged from the host egg. The two other parasitoids were differentiated by the color of the host egg. In case of doubt, records were made after the parasite emerged from the host egg. The percentage parasitism for each species was calculated from the total number of eggs parasitized during each period and the number parasitized by each species.

Overall parasitization and predation was 42%. *Anagrus* was the dominant species (27%) throughout the season, followed by the eulophid (11%). The incidence of *Oligosita* was inconsistent (8%), but when *Oligosita* showed an increase, the number of eulophids decreased and vice versa. However, the dominant mymarid had its share of host eggs unopposed by the two other egg parasitoids. \mathcal{J}

Occurrence of rice mealy bug in Tamil Nadu, India

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In December 1985, a severe incidence of the mealy bug *Heterococcus rehi* (Lindinger) occurred over an area of 100 ha in Annavasal, Pudukottai district, Tamil Nadu, India. White Ponni and IR20 raised in garden lands were severely infested in the postflowering stage. The nymph and adult populations ranged from 650 to 700 per hill. Infestation occurred in patches and

affected plants turned yellow, were severely stunted, and failed to produce panicles. Prolonged drought as a result of inadequate water supply probably accounted for the high population of mealy bug. \mathcal{J}

Effects of 6 granular insecticides on rice rhizosphere microflora in India

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Granular insecticides may influence the activity of rice rhizosphere microflora,

and the microflora may regulate decomposition, dissipation, and persistence of granular insecticides. In Bhubaneswar, rice soils had 165 fungi species, predominantly *Aspergillus*, *Cephalosporium*, *Curvularia*, *Neocosmospora*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus*, *Spicaria*, and *Trichoderma*; many species of facultative anaerobes such as *Escherichia*, *Aerobacter*, *Erwinia*, *Aeromonas*, *Streptococcus*, and *Bacillus*; and N-fixing bacteria such as *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Paucimobilis*.

We studied the effects of six commonly used granular insecticides on rice soil microflora in 1983 wet season (Jun-Dec). The insecticides were